

Summarizing for “P versus NP” Theorem and its Outcomes

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ABSTRACT

In this final work we present the final results obtained during our scientific work and collaboration on account of “P versus NP” theorem and tractability of NP-complete problems and other related questions.

Keywords: P versus NP, outcome, summary.

INTRODUCTION

The “P versus NP” theorem [1] is a classical approach of giving the question to the complexity and solution of any problem, which is defined as NP-complete class. During this time the problem was postponed [2] and still remains unsolved.

We give the results for parallel algorithms [3], data structures [4] and finite automata [5] on account of this respective and important question.

SUMMARY OF OUTCOMES

The parallel algorithms unfortunately don’t solve intractable NP-complete problems due to the fact that even if we would theoretically increase the number of solving threads, the complexity still depends on the size of the parameter of the problem according to big-O notation and, thus, it doesn’t matter even if we will get the infinite number of parallel threads, the problem will still stand on the point of N .

We have also shown that there is no effective data structure like priority queues or any other which could solve the same NP-complete problem in a reasonable amount of time, as when we will use it we will have to store the full number of cases and potential candidates which increases at least exponentially, if not in factorial memory space.

Finite automata and subset construction is also a method which don’t solve intractable problems lying in complexity class “NP” due to the fact that for general cases the complexity increases exponentially in number of spaces and steps required to build the verifying automaton.

CONCLUSION

Thus, we have presented the main outcomes and results for our pre-made work.

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